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Institut méditerranéen de biodiversité
et d'écologie - marine et continentale -

11th International Symposium on Syrphidae

5th – 10th September 2022

Barcelonnette, France

Programme and Abstracts

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Edited by Gabriel Nève

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Symposium logo

Logo by Lise Ropars, with a drawing by Jean-Yves Meunier based on his photograph of *Helophilus trivittatus*, taken at Fos-sur-Mer, Bouches-du-Rhône, on 24 May 2018.

Newly designated hoverfly (Diptera: Syrphidae) species of conservation concern and Prime Hoverfly Areas in Serbia

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Due to limited resources for conservation purposes, conservation efforts have to be precisely directed in a way that would ensure the protection of as many imperilled species as possible. To be able to do that, it is necessary to implement systematic sampling as a basis for conservation. Building on the work of Vujić et al. (2016), in the period from 2016. to 2018, systematic sampling of hoverflies on designated localities on the territory of Republic of Serbia was conducted. The aim of this study was to designate new species of conservation concern (PHA species) and additional Prime Hoverfly Areas (PHAs), based on the new records from recent field work. Methodology of Vujić et al. (2016) was followed, species or area had to meet at least one of the criteria in order to be denoted as PHA species or area. According to our results, 16 species met the requirements to be marked as PHA species, while seven areas met the criteria to be designated as PHAs. Additionally, designated areas were overlapped with Protected Areas, Prime Butterfly Areas and Important Bird Areas to determine the percentage of overlapping between new PHAs and areas which have some form of recognition and/or protection in Serbia. Results of this study can significantly contribute in planning future monitoring activities and creating conservation strategy for the preservation of important hoverfly species in Serbia. They also represent a solid foundation for alteration or expansion of legislative concerning this insect group.

Reference

Vujić, A., et al. 2016. Prime Hoverfly (Insecta: Diptera: Syrphidae) Areas (PHA) as a conservation tool in Serbia. *Biol. Cons.* 198, 22-32.

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